

Electrochemical CO reduction in zero-gap

electrolyzers necessitates careful water management.

Siddharth Gupta^{†#}, Gumaa A-El Nagar^{§†}, Andrii Solodaniuk^{†#}, Zhaoli Zhu^{†#}, Chaoqun Ma^{†#}, Flora Hahn^{†#}, Yu-Lin Tsai^{†§}, Matthew T. Mayer^{†##}.*

[†] Electrochemical conversion, Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie GmbH,
Hahn-Meitner-Platz 1, 14109, Berlin, Germany

[§]Chemistry Departement, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, 12613, Cairo, Egypt

[#] Institut für Chemie & Biochemie, Freie Universität Berlin, 14195, Berlin, Germany

[§] Institut für Chemie, Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin 10623, Germany

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Corresponding Author*

m.mayer@helmholtz-berlin.de

Abstract

Electrochemical CO reduction has emerged as a prospective approach to synthesize C_{2+} products in tandem with $CO_2 - CO$ electrolysis to minimize carbon losses associated with the $CO_2-CO_3^{2-}$ equilibrium. In this study, we explore electrochemical CO reduction and underscore the pertinent need for careful water management and highlight the differences between CO and CO_2 electrolysis. Employing Cu-based GDEs (without ionomers) for CO reduction (COR) in zero-gap electrolyzers led to primarily hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) contrary to CO_2 reduction where a spread of different products was observed. Incorporating an ionomer (Nafion) for CO fed Cu-based electrolyzers led to suppression of hydrogen evolution from 70 % FEs to < 20 % FEs. These results highlight the crucial need for water management in zero-gap electrolyzers to enable CO reduction, and also indicate substantial differences on changing the feed-gas (CO_2 vs CO). The cell configuration chosen was also shown to impact the selectivity. Nafion-free Cu GDEs for CO reduction showed lower selectivity towards H_2 in the catholyte-flow cell configuration indicating the effect of the cell configuration on local water management. These results together showed the unique challenges associated with operating CO electrolysis in zero-gap electrolyzers. Using K^+ as a probe for penetration depth of water in SEM-EDS measurements, differences in the potassium distribution across the cross-section of the gas diffusion layer were observed. *Operando* X-ray absorption spectroscopy and glovebox-assisted x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) were used to evaluate electronic effects of Nafion incorporation on Cu GDEs. From the spectroscopy we surmise that the effects of Nafion are limited to the transport of water, (solvated) cations, and potentially local pH modulation. Post electrochemistry surface speciation studies for CO and CO_2 fed electrolyser were also carried out which suggested a higher fraction of oxide speciation for the

CO fed electrolyzers also suggesting local pH differences due to the absence of the carbonate equilibria.

Introduction

The chemical sector is projected to have emissions of 200 Mt of CO₂ equivalents by 2050. Electrochemical carbon dioxide/monoxide conversion is a carbon negative approach for chemical synthesis that can help de-fossilize this sector and turn it from a carbon source to a carbon sink.¹

² The CO₂ - CO₃²⁻ equilibrium in alkaline CO₂ electrolyzers imposes a product dependent theoretical limitation on the single pass CO₂ conversion yields which for C₂₊ products like ethylene is 25%.³⁻⁷ Moreover, carbonate formation leads to a decrease in operational lifetimes due to salt precipitation blocking the porous gaseous pathway,⁸ and an increase in required overpotentials due to a gradual decrease in the bulk electrolyte pH.⁹⁻¹¹ Electrochemical CO reduction (eCOR) mitigates this carbon loss mechanism hindering industrial applicability of alkaline CO₂ electrolysis.^{3,4,12,13}

As CO₂ electrolysis to C₂₊ hydrocarbons proceeds with the formation of the important *CO intermediate, CO and CO₂R are hypothesized to share similar reaction pathways from the C-C coupling steps and beyond.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ This is experimentally observed in that Cu metal is, like for CO₂R, the only metal known showing appreciable activity towards C₂₊ products using CO as the feed gas.^{17,18} While mechanistically both COR and CO₂R are known to have similarities, experimentally, their different physical properties necessitate feed-gas dependent modulation of the catalytic microenvironment.¹⁹⁻²¹

The lower aq. phase solubility of CO (1 mM at 1 bar) in comparison to CO₂ (33 mM at 1 bar), warrants that the reaction interface is carefully managed to prevent large aq. diffusion path lengths which would impede high current density COR, more so than for CO₂R.^{9,11,22} While there

is yet to be a consensus on the reaction interphase recent reports have hinted towards the formation of double-phase boundaries as opposed to earlier reports of triple-phase boundaries enabling high currents in gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs).^{9,23,24} As the feed gas, CO, must diffuse through an aq. layer, minimizing the aq. diffusion path lengths becomes pertinent, especially for CO due to its much lower solubility in comparison to CO₂. To this end, ionomers/coatings which impart hydrophobicity to the catalyst layer are essential to minimize the water layer thickness and/or increase the density of three-phase boundary sites.^{19,25,26} Nafion, a perfluorinated sulfonic ionomer, has been widely used in the electrocatalysis community due to its role as a binder, but its fluorocarbon backbones also import hydrophobicity to the catalyst layer.²⁷⁻²⁹ Strategies to modify the catalyst layer and incorporate hydrophobic polymers to mitigate hydrogen evolution have previously been emphasized for both COR and CO₂R.³⁰⁻³³

In this study we compare COR and CO₂R and examine the increased need for catalyst layer functionalization for COR. Besides investigating influence of catalyst layer functionalization on CO₂R we also examine COR performances in zero-gap electrolyser and catholyte-flow electrolysers (flowing catholyte between the catalyst layer and the membrane) to assess the effect of the liquid electrolyte on the challenge of mitigating hydrogen evolution. To assess feed-gas dependent surface speciation we employed glovebox-assisted XPS, and *operando* XAS. These techniques were also extended to study the impact of Nafion incorporation on as-prepared Cu catalysts and investigate the impact of Nafion incorporation on the speciation during operation conditions.

1. Results and discussion

In this study we explore the need for careful water management during COR and how the water in the catalyst layer and subsequently product selectivity is affected by the choice of electrolyser

configuration, and hydrophobicity of the catalyst layer. To investigate these phenomena, we use Cu NPs (50-60nm, Sigma Aldrich) spray coated onto a Freudenberg H23C6 gas diffusion layer (GDL) as the cathode and Ir HSA (Fuel Cell Store) powders deposited on Ti frits as the anode. Differing amounts of Nafion content were incorporated in the cathode ink preparation step. The electrodes were tested in a custom made catholyte flow cell (1.5 cm², schematic in Figure S1a), and a zero-gap cell (8 cm²) developed by eChemicles Zrt (schematic in Figure S1b).^{6,34} 1 M KOH was used as the electrolyte across all measurements. Two 20 μm thick PiperION anion exchange membranes were used to separate the anode and cathode compartments, unless otherwise stated. A schematic of the entire experimental setup is given in Figure S2. The complete faradaic efficiencies of all detected products are plotted in the SI (SI Note 3), while only hydrogen, ethylene and CO/acetate are plotted here in some cases, for ease of data interpretation. Further experimental details are mentioned in the experimental section of the SI and can also be found in our previous works.^{7,35}

Uniqueness of CO reduction in zero-gap electrolyzers.

Our initial experiments on Cu-GDEs for CO electrolysis in zero-gap electrolyzers predominantly showed formation of hydrogen and very low COR product selectivities which was contrary to our observations for CO₂ fed electrolyzers.⁷ To further investigate this, we carried out experiments on CO and CO₂ fed zero-gap electrolyzers using replicate Cu GDEs. The results in Figure 1b (top row) showed considerable differences in the hydrogen and ethylene selectivities for CO and CO₂ fed electrolyzers. This led us to believe that the differences observed were to do with the differences in the physical properties of the two gases, specifically the aq. solubilities. We also carried out experiments in another cell configuration, catholyte-flow, to assess if the high hydrogen selectivity for CO-fed zero-gap electrolyzers was unique to the zero-gap configuration. The zero

gap experiments were conducted at 3.2 V full cell voltage which resulted in current densities between 75-100 mA cm² while the catholyte-flow experiments were carried out under constant current operation mode at 100 mAcm². Experiments across the two cell configurations were conducted for both CO and CO₂ fed electrolyzers and are shown in Figure 1b. These selectivity trends due to feed gas, and electrolyser differences are discussed independently.

Figure 1. Comparing zero-gap (upper row) and catholyte-flow electrolyzers (lower row) using replicate Cu GDEs. a) schematic of the cell configurations., b) selectivity towards hydrogen and ethylene under CO and CO₂ electrolysis, c) focused-ion beam (FIB) SEM-EDS micrographs and d) line scans showing variation of Cu (red), K (blue), and C (green) through the cross-section of the catalyst layer (CL) and gas diffusion layer (GDL).

Feed gas dependent behaviour:

Both electrolyzers, in Figure 1b, showed similar feed gas dependent selectivity behaviors, in that the hydrogen faradaic efficiency (FE) was considerably higher and ethylene FEs lower on using CO as the feed gas. These feed gas dependent trends could be attributed to the differences in the

aq. solubilities of CO and CO₂. Assuming the reaction takes place at a two-phase interface as recent studies have suggested²⁴, then the aq. solubilities of the two gases become a crucial factor governing the mass transport of the reactant and subsequently the currents towards CO/CO₂ reduction. Additionally, if majority of the reaction took place at the triple phase boundaries, then feed gas dependent behaviors would be less pronounced. Our results too suggest that the reaction in our electrolyser configurations, takes place predominantly at the two-phase boundary. Therefore, to enable high current density COR, incorporation of additives, hydrophobic ionomers, would be essential to manage the water in the catalyst layer and minimize aq. diffusion path lengths.

Cell configuration dependent behaviour:

Figure 1b also highlights interesting differences on moving from zero-gap electrolysers to catholyte-flow electrolysers for CO reduction experiments. A recent study by Ayyuub et.al., has also hinted at electrolyser configuration-based differences in COR performances.³⁶ The H₂ FE for CO-fed catholyte-flow electrolysers was considerably lower (50% compared to 75% in the zero-gap case) while the ethylene selectivities were higher. Our hypothesis explaining this observation is based around the different propensities to flooding depending on the electrolyser used. For zero-gap electrolysers the unintended crossover of (solvated) cations, has previously been reported.^{5,7,37} The (solvated) cations that crossover do so along with water and are known to breakthrough the catalyst layer (CL) and gas diffusion layer (GDL). Recent studies with X-ray based approaches have observed the presence of cations and water in the GDL suggesting the essential need for water management, especially for CO fed electrolysers.^{38,39} In our study, we use potassium as a probe for water and image the cross-section of the GDL, shown in Figure 1c and d. A focused ion beam (FIB) was used to mill and prepare the cross-sections which were subsequently imaged and

analyzed using an SEM-EDS. Our results using potassium as a probe for water penetration depths show subtle differences in the potassium concentration across the two electrolyzer configurations. For the zero-gap electrolyser significant potassium signal was from beneath the CL, deep into the GDL which hints towards the CL being flooded. As metallic catalysts are hydrophilic in nature (especially so on the application of bias), we would assume that presence of potassium and thereby water in the GDL would imply that the CL has significant amounts of water. This agrees with our hypothesis of COR currents being limited in this electrolyser configuration due to large aq. diffusion path lengths. However, in the catholyte-flow configuration due to the presence of a flowing electrolyte with the same concentration on either side of the membrane the driving force for the electrolyte ions to flood through the catalyst layer is lower. Experimentally this is observed from the SEM-EDS in Figure 1b and also evidenced indirectly from the selectivity data which shows lower hydrogen FEs and increased COR currents for the catholyte-flow case.

Figure 2 Effects of Nafion incorporation for CO fed Cu-GDE in zero-gap electrolyzers a) FE% towards hydrogen and ethylene., b) focused-ion beam (FIB) SEM-EDS micrographs and c) line scans showing variation of Cu (red), K (blue), and C (green) through the cross-section of the catalyst layer (CL) and gas diffusion layer (GDL).

To mitigate this issue of elevated hydrogen FEs in the zero-gap electrolyser, Nafion was incorporated into the catalyst layer. Catalysts with 9 % Nafion were tested in the zero-gap electrolyser at 3.2 V where it was observed that the hydrogen efficiencies were drastically reduced and current towards COR products increased as is shown in Figure 2a. Nafion, a perfluorosulfonic acid, consists of hydrophilic sulfonic groups and a hydrophobic fluorocarbon backbone. When the sulfonic groups face the catalyst, the perfluorinated backbone faces outwards minimizing the migration of water to the catalyst thus limiting HER and promoting eCOR. Nafion being a cation exchange ionomer also precludes transport of locally produced hydroxide ions thereby increasing the local alkalinity.^{27,29,40-42}. (The complete product distribution is given in Figure S3). SEM-EDS analysis of FIB milled samples (Figure 2b,c) containing Nafion showed very interesting behavior. It was observed that most of the potassium was removed from the catalyst layer and was found to be in the GDL suggesting that the Nafion helps manage water around the CL and therefore enable higher COR currents. These results are summarized in the scheme shown in Figure 3. We hypothesize that incorporation of Nafion increases local CO concentrations by either decreasing aq. diffusion path lengths or facilitating more three-phase boundaries in comparison to the electrodes without Nafion. On the other hand, CO₂R on electrodes without Nafion still has sufficiently large local CO₂ concentrations (in comparison to COR due to higher aq. solubilities), resulting in the observed CO₂R current densities.

Impact of Nafion on the transport of reactants

Figure 3 Impact of Nafion on the transport of reactants - CO, CO₂, and the proton source for a) COR with Nafion incorporation, b) COR without Nafion and c) CO₂R without Nafion.

Selectivity trends on Nafion incorporation

To further investigate the effect of Nafion incorporation on the electrochemical behaviour, we conducted COR and CO₂R experiments with varying amounts of Nafion. Four different Nafion amounts (0, 9 %, 13 %, 26 %) were tested between 2.8 V - 3.2 V. Catalysts with 9 % Nafion, were tested in a wider voltage range of 2.8 V to 4.0 V. Each voltage was measured using new catalysts, membranes and fresh electrolyte. The data points correspond to average values taken from experiments lasting for at least 1 hour.

Figure 4 Electrochemical characterization of CO-fed zero-gap electrolyzers. a) Effect of Nafion incorporation on product selectivity, b) Current and FE over an hour of experiments using 9% Nafion containing catalyst measured at 3.8 V, c) Current and selectivity trends for 9% Nafion containing catalyst tested between 2.8 V and 4 V, d) 3 hour test at 3.2 V for catalyst containing 9% Nafion.

The Nafion concentration dependent selectivity trends for CO-fed zero-gap electrolyser are presented in Figure 4a, where it is seen that for the two intermediate Nafion concentrations (9 % and 13 %) the selectivity and currents are rather invariant but show significant changes compared to the case without Nafion, as has been discussed earlier. Further increasing the Nafion amount resulted in an increase in the hydrogen FEs. (Complete dataset in Figure S3 – Figure S5) Correlating the product selectivities with macroscale hydrophobicity (evaluated by contact angle measurements and given in Fig S6) it is seen that an increase in the contact angle results in a decrease in the hydrogen selectivities. This suggests that incorporating Nafion into the catalyst

layer impacts local hydrophobicity and this is possibly linked with the mitigation of the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Furthermore, the effect of Nafion incorporation was also studied for CO₂-fed zero-gap electrolyzers (Figure S7- Figure S10) where it was observed that an increase in Nafion concentrations led to an increase in the selectivities towards CO, which also suggested transport limitations for the hydrogen sources. Figure 4c plots the voltage dependent selectivity trends for catalysts containing 9% Nafion, which show a surprisingly invariant selectivity response to changing voltage. Current densities of 300mA/cm² were achieved at 4 V applied voltage using Ir-based anodes which were not fully optimized for alkaline COR. Recent studies have reported the crucial role of anode process on the overall cell stability and voltage ⁴³ suggesting our anode catalyst requires further optimization. A 3-hour long stability test was also conducted which showed stable current response and selectivity behaviour, given in Figure 4d.

Examining surface speciation by X-ray methods

To examine if Nafion incorporation or the feed gas had any effects on the surface speciation of Cu GDEs, we employed two X-ray-based approaches. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to probe the surface speciation post electrochemistry for which samples were transferred in an inert atmosphere from the test-bench to the spectrometer. Differences in the speciation were observed for the catalysts tested. First, there was a feed gas dependent speciation difference, seen in Figure 5a, wherein electrodes tested under COR conditions showed a considerably higher oxide signal in the Cu LMM auger analysis in comparison to electrodes tested under CO₂R. This indicated subtle differences in local pH conditions due to the absence of the CO₂ - CO₃²⁻ which would result in higher local alkalinity potentially leading to stabilization of the oxide phases. Second, the incorporation of Nafion was also seen to subtly affect the speciation. Catalysts devoid of Nafion showed predominantly metallic behavior while incorporating Nafion into the catalyst

layer led to a higher fraction of oxide phases. This once again could be due to Nafion locally trapping hydroxide ions, which increases the local pH and therefore stabilizes the oxide phases. Nafion being an ionomer that conducts cations would ideally exclude the transport of anions and thereby trap the local hydroxide ions. The impact of differing amounts of Nafion on the Cu surface speciation of as-prepared samples is given in Figure S11.

Figure 5. X-ray spectroscopy analysis. a) Cu LMM Auger spectra measured using glovebox-assisted XPS for catalysts with and without Nafion and tested under CO and CO₂ feed gases. b) Cu K-edge XANES spectra, c) FT-EXAFS spectra

The XPS approach was an ex-situ approach where the catalysts were removed from applied bias and tested later, and therefore, any surface oxidation post removal of bias could not be ruled out. To carry out *operando* studies we conducted X-ray absorption spectroscopy (XAS) measurements at the KMC-2 beamline at BESSY-II. The XAS results (Figure 5b, c) on the other hand showed very little differences either on the incorporation of Nafion or depending on the feed gas used. On the application of bias, the oxide signal visible for measurements at open-circuit quickly gave way to metallic features and similar behaviour was observed for all the tested conditions. We

hypothesized that these differences between the XPS and XAS analysis could firstly arise due to XPS measurements being conducted without any applied electrode bias or because XAS is a bulk-sensitive technique and therefore any surface oxide signal would be obfuscated by the bulk Cu signal. For more precise *operando* surface analysis, future experiments with either smaller nanoparticle sizes, to increase the surface-bulk ratio, or a move to lower X-ray energies would be necessary.

2. Conclusion

In this study we highlighted the significant differences between electrochemical CO and CO₂ reduction, which are essential to consider for future COR research. The necessity for careful water management for CO electrolysis due to its low aq. solubility was laid out. These water management challenges across different cell configurations varied and it was observed that zero-gap electrolyzers required more careful management. SEM-EDS on FIB milled electrodes showed a potassium distribution in the thickness of the CL/GDL that was dependent on the electrolyzer configuration, and ionomer functionalization. Incorporating Nafion in the catalyst ink prior to spray deposition was seen to have a beneficial impact, suppressing HER to around 20% FE. A systematic study on Nafion concentration dependent selectivity trends for both CO and CO₂ reduction underscored the potential impact of both (solvated) cations and water in the catalyst layer. XPS studies on CO and CO₂ fed Cu GDEs tested in zero-gap electrolyzers showed significant speciation variations indicating different catalytic microenvironments due to the presence/absence of the CO₂ - carbonate equilibrium. Catalysts with and without Nafion also showed differences in surface speciation due to potential differences in local alkalinity.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

Matthew T. Mayer.

Author Contributions

S.G: Conceived the study, experimental planning, electrochemical experiments, SEM, XPS and XAS - data fitting and analysis and preparing manuscript draft. G.A.E.N: Experimental planning, FIB-SEM, XPS, XAS measurements, and regular discussions. A.S: Electrode preparation and electrochemical testing. Z.Z: Electrode preparation and XAS measurements. CM: Electrode preparation. Y.L.T: XAS measurements. M.T.M: Assisted with data analysis, regular discussions and commented on the manuscript. All authors except contributed to the XAS beamtime measurements.

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